

Consumer Perception and Awareness towards Green Products in the Era of Viksit Bharat (2047)

Dr. Shweta Mishra ¹

¹ Assistant Professor, Faculty of Commerce St. John's College, Agra.

ABSTRACT

In the era of VIKSIT BHARAT, sustainable development and environmental responsibility have emerged as central pillar of India's growth. The increasing environmental challenges and policy emphasis on green growth have accelerated the demand for eco- friendly and sustainable products. This paper presents an overview of the concept of green marketing in the context of the rapidly growing Indian Industrial sector. With increasing environmental awareness consumers are gradually shifting their preferences towards eco- friendly products. Since natural resources are limited, it has become essential for marketers to use resources efficiently and promote sustainable practices. The Promotion and adoption of green products and environmentally friendly technologies play a crucial role in conserving natural resources and achieving sustainable development consequently many companies are adopting green market strategies to encourage the use of eco- friendly products and services. Despite these efforts, the acceptance of green marketing among consumers remains relatively less. This is mainly due to insufficient awareness about eco-friendly products, ineffective promotional activities by manufacturers, and the lack of standardized government rules and regulations. In this context, this paper aims to examine the consumer perceptions toward environmentally friendly products using a factor analysis approach and enhancing consumer awareness through education, transparent eco- labelling, and government –supported awareness campaigns can significantly improve consumer perception and acceptance of green products.

Keywords: Green Marketing, Green products and technologies, Consumer Perception, Eco-friendly.

1. INTRODUCTION

Environmental degradation, climate change, and excessive exploitation of natural resources have raised serious concerns about sustainable development. In response, countries worldwide are shifting towards eco-friendly practices and green consumption. In India, the concept of Viksit Bharat reflects the nation's aspiration to become a developed economy while maintaining social equity and environmental sustainability. Green products are designed to minimise environmental impact throughout their life cycle, from production to disposal. As consumers play vital role in determining market demand, understanding their perception and awareness towards green products are essential. This paper focuses on how Indian consumers perceive green products and how awareness levels are evolving in alignment with the vision promoted by the Government of India. Green marketing refers to the process of promoting, producing and selling products and services that are environmentally friendly and safe for society. It focuses on reducing environmental damage and encouraging sustainable consumption. The concept become popular after the rise of environmental awareness and was strongly supported by organisations like the American Marketing Association, which defines green marketing as the marketing of products that are presumed to be environmentally safe. Examples include organic food products, energy-efficient appliances, biodegradable packaging, electric vehicles and eco-friendly personal care products.

2. CONSUMER PERCEPTION TOWARDS GREEN PRODUCTS

Consumer perception towards green products refers to the way individuals understand, evaluate and form opinions about products that are environmentally friendly and sustainable. In recent years, increasing environmental concerns such as climate change, population and resource depletion have significantly influenced consumer attitudes and behaviour. As a result, green products have gained importance in both academic research and market practices. This concept is central to green marketing and sustainability research, as it influences purchasing decisions aimed growing environmental awareness. Positive perceptions often stem from beliefs that these products benefit the surroundings health and society, though barriers like higher costs persist. There are several key factors shape the perceptions.

- Environmental awareness and concerns
- Product Attributes:
- Social and psychological influences
- Demographic variables

- Marketing and trust

3. VIKSIT BHARAT AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT:

Viksit Bharat refers to India's vision of becoming a fully developed nation with strong economic growth, social progress, technological advancement and improved quality of life for all citizens. The vision being promoted by government of India with a target year of 2047 (100 years of independence). The main focus of Viksit Bharat includes:

- Economic development and job creation
- Digital transformation
- Infrastructure development
- Social inclusion
- Environmental protection

Sustainable development means development that meets present needs without harming the ability of future generations to meet their own needs. This concept was defined by the World Commission on Environment and Development in 1987. It is based on three pillars:

- Economic Sustainability
- Social sustainability
- Environmental sustainability.

The vision of Viksit Bharat integrates economic growth with environmental responsibility. Sustainable consumption and production are key pillars of this vision. Government-led initiatives such as Swachh Bharat Mission, promotion of renewable energy, plastic waste management rules and support for green entrepreneurship have contributed to increase public awareness about environmental sustainability.

4. REVIEW OF LITERATUE

Earlier studies such as Singh and pandey (2018) and kumar amd kumar (2020) also concluded that awareness positively affects purchase decisions, but it is not the sole determinant of buying behaviour. Moreover, demographic variables like income, age, and education play a crucial role in shaping awareness levels, with higher income and educated consumers showing greater environmental consciousness. Balagopalan and jeyaramya (2025) found that consumers have a

favourable perception of eco-friendly FMCG products however concerns about high prices and limited availability restrict adoption. Similarly, Kumar 2025 highlighted that brand, trust, perceived effectiveness and environmental concern significantly influence consumer perception and purchase intention. The literature reveals that consumer awareness and perception towards green products in India have improved significantly over the last decade. However a substantial gap still exists between awareness and actual purchasing behaviour. Factors such as price, availability, trust and socio economic conditions continue to influence consumer decision. Behaviour. Zeynalova & Namazova, (2022) conducted research with the objectives of determining the factors that affect the purchase decision, intentions, awareness, attitude, and behaviour towards green products. The results indicated that 84% of the respondents were aware of the green products and their Consumption was based on the associated indicators of the products, like their environmentally friendly nature, price, brands, and advertising. The influence of the indicators varies according to the demographic profile of the respondents. The study shows that respondents were partially sensitive towards the environment. Sinha and Gupta (2025) found that 72.5% of consumers were aware of green products although actual purchase rates were lower, reflecting a gap between awareness and behaviour. Similarly, Godara et al. (2025) observed that awareness levels are significantly influenced by digital media, education and socio-economic status, particularly among urban consumers.

5. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Green Marketing is the requirement of today era. The Earth has been surrounded with waste made by man. The Earth should be a better place to live in for us and for our next generations. The only way is to protect the Earth is by spreading the knowledge and awareness about the green marketing.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY:

- To study the awareness of consumers in Agra district regarding green marketing
- Identifying the factors influencing the buying decision of consumers regarding eco-friendly products.
- To analyses the reasons for non- usage of green products by consumers.

HYPOTHESIS

H01: There is no significant difference level of awareness about green marketing among consumers.

H02: There is no significant influence of factors (price, quality, brand image, environmental concern and availability).

H03: There is no significant reasons affecting the non- usage of green products by consumers.

6. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study reveals to know the consumers' perception and awareness towards green products in Agra city. I have used Descriptive as well as Analytical Research for the study.

Data Sources

For this study I have used Primary and Secondary data. Primary data was collected from 100 Respondent in Agra city, which representing both genders, different age groups, different educational level, and different income level.

Sampling Design

For this study the sample size is 100 respondents from Agra City.

Data Collection Method

A structured questionnaire with a 5 point-likert scale was used to analysis consumer perception towards green products and the awareness towards ecological products. The basic components, namely the consumer's awareness level, reason to purchase and reasons for not purchasing, consumer purchase intention, and source of information, have been considered when developing the questionnaire for this research paper. The primary data was collected and analysed with the help of the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS). The secondary data was collected from books, journals, published theses, and websites. The collected data was analyzed with the help of the percentage method.

Reliability Statistics	
Cronbach's Alpha	No. of Items
.952	20

Table 1: Data Analysis and Interpretation
Source: Author Compiled

Here the researcher applied Cronbach's Alpha test to find out the reliability of the questionnaire. The obtained value of 0.952 for 20 items indicates excellent internal consistency among variables. This suggests that the instrument used for data collection is highly reliable and suitable for further statistical analysis.

For this study I have taken five major demographic factors to know about the gender of respondents, age group, education level, annual income and occupation.

S.NO	Variables	No. of respondent (100)	Percentage
1.	Gender	Male	20 25 %
		Female	80 75 %
2.	Age Group	Below 18	2 1.9%
		18 to 20	10 13 %
		21 to 30	48 44.4 %
		31 to 40	20 18.5 %

		41 to 50	20	22.2 %
3.	Educational Qualification	Illiterate	0	0 %
		School	6	5.6 %
		Graduate	35	34.3 %
		Post Graduate	40	39.8 %
		Professional	20	20.4 %
4.	Income	Below 20,000	43	41.7 %
		21,000- 50,000	12	13 %
		50,000- 1,00,000	05	8.3 %
		1,00,000- 2,00,000	17	15.7 %
		2,00,000 and above	23	21.3 %
5.	Occupation	Agriculture	0	0 %
		Business	6	5.6 %

		Private employee	31	32.4 %
		Government employee	10	11.1 %
		Student	53	50.9 %

Table 2: Demographic status of consumer
Source: Author Compiled

The above table 1 clearly shows that the demographic level of respondents, out of 108 respondents,

- The majority (75%) of the respondents are female.
- The majority (44.4%) of the respondents belong to the age group of 21 – 30 years.
- The majority (39.8%) of the respondents are qualified as post – graduate.
- The majority (41.7%) of the respondents are earning less the 20,000 Rs per month.
- The majority (50.9%) of the respondents are students.

Section A

1. I am aware of the concept of green product.

Rating Scale		Percentage of Respondents	Mean Score
Strongly Agree	5	50.9	4.14
Agree	4	35.2	
Neutral	3	9.3	

Disagree	2	0.9	
Strongly Disagree	1	3.7	
Total		100	

Table 3 Awareness level of consumer about green product

Source: Author Compiled

Figure 1: Awareness level of consumer about green product

Source: Author Compiled

The calculated mean score of 4.14 on a 5-point scale indicates high level of agreement among respondents regarding the awareness of green products. Since the mean value is closer to 5 (strongly Agree), it clearly reflects that the majority of consumers possess good awareness and positive perception towards green products

2. I am aware that green products are environmental friendly.

Rating Scale		Percentage of Respondents	Mean Score
Strongly Agree	5	49.5	

Agree	4	36.1	4.26
Neutral	3	9.3	
Disagree	2	1.0	
Strongly Disagree	1	4.1	
Total		100	

Table 4: Awareness level of consumer about green product
Source: Author Compiled

Figure 2: Awareness level of consumer about green product
Source: Author Compiled

The data shows that a significant proportion of respondents have a positive awareness of green products being environmentally friendly. A majority of respondents 49.5% are Strongly Agree and 36.1% are Agree, indicating that 85.6% of the respondents hold a favourable opinion towards the statements. Only a small percentage of respondents expressed uncertainty or disagreement, with 9.3% remaining neutral,

1.0% disagreeing and 4.1% Strongly Disagree. The Mean Value of 4.26 on a 5 point scale further confirms a high level of agreement and awareness among respondents.

1. I am aware that green products help in reducing environmental pollution

<i>Rating Scale</i>		<i>Percentage of Respondents</i>	<i>Mean Value</i>
Strongly Agree	5	48.1	4.26
Agree	4	37.0	
Neutral	3	10.2	
Disagree	2	1.9	
Strongly Disagree	1	2.8	
<i>Total</i>		<i>100</i>	

Table 5: Green products help in reducing environmental pollution
Source: Author Compiled

Figure 3: Green products help in reducing environmental pollution
 Source: Author Compiled

The data shows that a large proportion of respondents are aware that a green product helps in reducing environmental pollution. A majority of respondent 48.1 % Strongly Agree and 37.0% Agree, indicating that approximately 85% Of respondents have a positive perception towards the statement. A smaller percentage 10.2% remains neutral, suggesting some respondents’ are unsure or lack complete awareness. Very few respondents expressed disagreement, with 1.9% disagrees which indicates minimal negative perception. The mean value of 4.26 confirms a high level of agreement as it is close to Strongly Agree on the likert-scale.

2. I have seen advertisements related to green products.

Rating Scale		Percentage of Respondents	Mean Value
Strongly Agree	5	32.4	3.95
Agree	4	39.8	
Neutral	3	21.3	

Disagree	2	3.7	
Strongly Disagree	1	2.8	
Total		100	

Table 6: Advertisements related to green products

Source: Author Compiled

Figure 4: Advertisements related to green products

Source: Author Compiled

The majority of respondents show a positive response. 32.4% respondents are Strongly Agree and 39.8% respondents are just agreeing by indicating that advertisement related to green products. 21.3% respondents are Neutral and a very small percentage of respondents are Disagree. The mean value is 3.95 which are very much close to 4, indicating an overall, high level of awareness and exposure to green product advertisement.

- I am aware of government initiatives promoting sustainable products under Viksit Bharat.

Rating Scale		Percentage of Respondents	Mean Value
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Strongly Agree	5	32.4	3.94
Agree	4	40.7	
Neutral	3	19.4	
Disagree	2	3.7	
Strongly Disagree	=.1	3.7	
Total		100	

Table 7: Government Initiatives Promoting Sustainable Products
Source: Author Compiled

Figure 5: Government Initiatives Promoting Sustainable Products
Source: Author Compiled

The above table represents the respondents' level of agreement towards the green products. it is found out that a majority of respondents 40.7% are agreed with the statement showing a positive inclination towards

green products. Further 19.4% of respondents have shown a neutral attitude, suggesting that a considerable portion of consumers are indifferent. On the other side only 3.7% of respondents are disagreed and strongly disagreed showing a negative perception. The mean value is 3.94 which is close to 4 indicates that on an average, respondents tend to agree with the statement.

1. Green products are safer for health:

Rating Scale		Percentage of Respondents	Mean Score
Strongly Agree	5	35.2	
Agree	4	44.5	
Neutral	3	16.7	4.09
Disagree	2	1.9	
Strongly Disagree	1	1.9	
Total		100	

Table 8: Green Products are Safer for Health. Annual In
Source: Author Compiled

Figure 6: Green Products are Safer for Health
 Source: Author Compiled

The calculated mean score of 4.10 on a 5 point scale indicates a high level of agreement among respondents. The majority of participants have expressed a favourable perception towards green products, as reflected by the high percentages of Agree (44.5%) and Strongly Agree (35.2%). Only a very small proportion of respondents reported negative opinion, with 1.9% each selecting Disagree and Strongly Disagree, while 16.7% remained Neutral. This clearly shows that negative perception towards green products is minimal. Overall, the findings suggest that consumers are aware of and positively inclined towards green products, indicating a growing acceptance and preference for environmentally friendly products in the market. The high mean score further supports the conclusion that green products are well received and hold a strong position in consumer perception.

3. Green products are better for environmental protection

Rating Scale		Percentage of Respondents	Mean Score
5	Strongly Agree	34.6	
4	Agree	44.9	

3	Neutral	16.8	4.09
2	Disagree	1.9	
1	Strongly Disagree	1.9	
	TOTAL	100	

Table 9: Green Products are Better for Environmental Protection
Source: Author Compiled

Figure 7: Green Products are better for Environmental Protection
Source: Author Compiled

It is observed that a significant majority of respondents hold a positive perception towards green products. Specifically, 44.9% of respondents agree and 34.6% of respondents are strongly agreed. This indicates that nearly 79.5% of the total respondents believe that green products contribute positively to environmental protection. On the other hand 16.8% of respondents remain neutral, suggesting that a moderate proportion of individuals are either unsure or lack sufficient awareness regarding the environmental protection.

4. I believe green products are of good quality

Rating Scale		Percentage of Respondents	Mean Score
Strongly Agree	5	39.8	4.10
Agree	4	38.9	
Neutral	3	16.7	
Disagree	2	0.9	
Strongly Disagree	1	3.7	
Total		100	

Source: Author Compiled

Figure 8: Green Products are of Good Quality
Source: Author Compiled

A significant majority of respondents 39.8% are strongly agree and 38.9% are agree, showing that the respondents have a favourable opinion about the quality of green products. This reflects a high level of trust and acceptance of green products in terms of quality. On the other hand,

16.7% of respondents remain neutral, suggesting that a moderate proportion of consumers are either uncertain or lack of sufficient experience with green products. Only a very small percentage of respondents expressed negative opinion, with 0.9% disagreeing and 3.7% strongly disagreeing, indicating minimal dissatisfaction. The mean score of 4.10 on a 5 point likert scale further supports the conclusion that overall perception is strongly positive and leans towards agreement.

5. Using green products helps in sustainable development:

Rating Scale		Percentage of Respondents	Mean Score
Strongly Agree	5	38.9	4.15
Agree	4	42.6	
Neutral	3	14.8	
Disagree	2	1.9	
Strongly Disagree	1	1.9	
Total		100	

Table 11: Green Products helps in sustainable development.
Source: Author Compiled

Figure 9: Green Products helps in sustainable development
Source: Author Compiled

A significantly majority of respondents have expressed agreement, with 42.6% agreeing and 38.9% strongly agreeing, making it evident that most positive impact of green products on sustainability. Only a small proportion of respondents remain neutral 14.8% suggesting limited uncertainty, a very negligible percentage 1.9% each disagree or strongly disagree, indicating minimal opposition to the idea. The mean score of 4.15 on a 5 point likert scale further reinforces this conclusion, showing a high level of overall agreement among respondents.

6. Buying green product is responsible behaviour:

Rating Scale		Percentage of Respondents	Mean Score
Strongly Agree	5	38.9	4.14
Agree	4	40.7	
Neutral	3	16.7	

Disagree	2	2.8	
Strongly Disagree	1	0.9	
Total			100

Table12: Buying green product is responsible behaviour.
Source: Author Compiled

Figure 10: Buying green product is responsible behaviour
Source: Author Compiled

A large proportion of respondents, 40.7% agree and 38.9% strongly agree. This reflects a high level of awareness and acceptance of environmentally responsible consumption. Only a small percentage of respondents expressed negative views with 2.8% Disagree and 0.9% strongly Disagree, which is almost negligible. Meanwhile, 16.7% remains Neutral indicating some respondents may lack strong awareness on the issue. The mean value is 4.14 on a 5 point scale further confirms that the overall attitude is highly positive and leans towards agreement.

Section C

Particulars	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Dis-Agree	Strongly Disagree	Mean Value
	(5)	(4)	(3)	(2)	(1)	

Environmental concern influences my decision to buy green products	29.6	41.7	2.8	2.8	2.8	4.16
Price affects my decision to purchase green products	13.0	51.9	25.0	5.6	2.8	3.67
Brand reputation influences me to purchase green products.	15.7	52.8	20.7	6.5	1.9	3.74
Availability of green products influences my buying decision.	17.6	48.1	21.3	6.5	1.9	3.73
Eco-labels and certification influence my trust in green products.	28.7	37.0	17.6	6.5	2.8	3.60

Table 13: Factors influencing purchase decision
Source: Author Compiled

Factors influencing purchase decision.

- Majority respondents agree 41.7% and Strongly Agree respondents are 29.6%.. Very few respondents are Neutral and Disagree. The mean value is 4.16 it shows the environmental concern is the most important factor influencing purchase decisions. Consumers are highly aware and motivated by environmental issues.
- In the second factor the majority of respondents are agree 51.9% but some of the respondents are neutral 25.0%. And few respondents are Disagree 5.6%. It shows that price is an important but moderate factor. Consumers consider price, but it is not the strongest influence.
- In the third factor majority of respondents are agree 52.8% and 15.7% of respondents are Strongly Agree. The mean value is 3.74.

This represents that Brand reputation has a significant positive influence on buying behaviour. Trusted brands encourage green purchases.

- The fourth factors shows that majority of respondents are agree 48.1%. Some of the respondents show neutral response 21.3%. The mean value is 3.73 which show that Availability plays a moderately strong role. Easy access to green products increases purchase likelihood.
- The fifth factor tells us that majority of respondents are agree 37.0% and 28.7% of respondents are Strongly Agree. Whereas, some of the respondents are Neutral in their response. 17.6%. the mean value is 3.60 which shows the lowest among the other factors. Eco- labels build consumer trust, but their influence is comparatively lower than other factors.

Section D

<i>Particulars</i>	<i>Strongly Agree</i> (5)	<i>Agree</i> (4)	<i>Neutral</i> (3)	<i>Dis-Agree</i> (2)	<i>Strongly Disagree</i> (1)	<i>Mean Value</i>
Green products are more expensive than regular products	18.5	42.6	24.1	9.3	5.6	3.59
Green products are not easily available in the market	16.7	40.7	24.1	15.7	2.8	3.53
I am not fully informed about the benefits of green products.	8.3	38.0	23.1	24.1	6.5	3.18
I doubt the authenticity of	8.3	38.0	31.5	16.7	5.6	3.27

green products claims.						
Lack of promotion reduces my interest in purchasing green products.	7.4	44.4	24.1	18.5	5.6	3.30

Table 14: Reasons for non-usage of green products:
Source: Author Compiled

Reasons for non-usage of green products

- The above table represents the respondents' opinion regarding various barriers and concerns related to green products. Green products are more expensive than regular products, a majority of respondents expressed with 42.6% agreed and 18.5% are strongly agreed. This shows that mostly consumers perceive green products as costlier alternatives making price a major barrier to adoption.
- Secondly, 40.7% of respondents are agreed and 16.7% of respondents are strongly agreed with the statement that green products are not easily available. This suggests that limited availability is another factor affecting consumer purchase decision.
- Thirdly, while 38% respondents are agreed and 24.1% of respondents are disagreed with the statement that they are not fully informed about the benefits of green products and 23.1% remained neutral, indicating that although awareness exists, complete knowledge about benefits is still lacks among many consumers.
- Further 38% of respondents are agreed and 31.5% were neutral about the statement that they doubt the authenticity of green product claims. This may be due to the issues like misleading advertisements or lack of proper certification.
- Lastly, 44.4% of respondents are agreed and 7.4% respondents are strongly agreed about the statement that lack of promotion reduces their interest in purchasing green products. It highlights that insufficient promotion and marketing efforts significantly affect consumer interest.

7. CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

- Based on the analysis of the data, it can be concluded that consumers exhibit a high level of awareness and a positive perception towards green products. a majority of respondents agree that green products

are environmentally friendly, which reflects growing environmental consciousness among consumers.

- The high mean score further supports the conclusion that awareness regarding the benefits of green products is strong. This indicates that initiatives promoting sustainability and green consumption in the era of Viksit Bharat are effectively influencing consumer attitudes.
- Therefore, it can be inferred that increased awareness and positive perception are likely to encourage consumers to adopt and purchase green products in the future.
- Overall findings indicate that although consumers have a positive inclination towards green products, several barriers hinder their adoption. The key challenges identified include high price, limited availability, and lack of effective promotion, incomplete awareness and doubts about authenticity. Among these price, and availability emerge as the most significant factors influence consumer behaviour.
- The findings indicate that consumers have a favourable awareness and perceptions towards green products, which reflects a growing inclination towards environmentally friendly products in the context of Viksit Bharat.
- The results reveal that consumers exhibits a favourable perception and awareness towards green products, supporting the ideas that green marketing initiatives are positively influencing consumer attitudes in the context of Viksit Bharat.
- This analysis clearly indicates that respondents possess strong awareness regarding the environmental benefits of green products. The high mean score and dominant agreement responses suggest that consumer awareness is well established, which can positively influence their perception and purchasing behaviour toward green products.
- Overall, consumer perception towards green products is generally positive but influenced by multiple factors such as awareness, price, quality and trust. A favourable perception leads to higher acceptance and purchase intention, whereas negative perceptions can hinder the growth of green markets. Therefore, business and policymakers must focus on increasing awareness, ensuring product quality, maintaining reasonable pricing and building trust to promote sustainable consumption.

8. SUGGESTIONS

The findings of the research allowed the authors to formulate the following suggestions for the stakeholders to improve the situation with green marketing:

- The government should actively promote green marketing initiatives, as they contribute towards environmental protection and public health.
- Companies should adopt more attractive and effective promotional strategies to attract consumers by making them aware of the benefits of green marketing.
- More innovations are required to expand the range of green products as they limit the purchase patterns of consumers' choices.
- Customer awareness programs should be organised to educate customers about the benefits of green products and encourage them to adopt it.
- Authentication by official license must be issued for verified and genuine green products to protect the trust of consumers and help identify fake products.
- Companies can boost the sale of green products by offering discounts to customers, which will help customers buy green products and solve the issue of expensiveness.
- The trust of the customers must be preserved by ensuring that, they receive quality and genuine products.
- There is a need for more varieties of green products, such as school bags, pencils, chalk, and other stationery items, which will create awareness about green marketing among school-students

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